

THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL DEFENSE MECHANISMS IN THE PERSONALITY AND ITS TEMPERAMENT IN SOCIETY

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Annotation: this article examines the problem of an individual's adaptation to interpersonal relationships in society during social life. The essence of adaptation is noted as a complex of protective behavioral reactions of a person, including individual psychological characteristics such as temperament and psychological defense mechanisms. Research work in this regard is devoted to the interrelation of the mechanisms of temperament and psychological protection.

Keywords: adaptation, coping behavior, temperament, psychological protection, psychological defense mechanisms.

Dynamically changing conditions in different areas of life affect a person's activities, including the following aspects, his personal condition, work activity, the quality of efficiency of the work performed, the relationship with the people around him. In today's developing society, stressors, conflicts in various HIL are fraught with conflicts, demands that cause States and negative feelings of internal discomfort of the individual are concerns. The individual falls into difficult life situations, using his existing knowledge and personal experience, he tries to adapt to the environment and seeks to improve his mental state. F.Berezin distinguished two important aspects of adaptation: the establishment of the optimal relationship between man and the environment and the features of creating adequate coordination in mental and physiological states. In the development of most adaptation reactions, two can be observed Ham in which: the initial stage of "urgent" imperfect adaptation and the subsequent stage are the stage of perfect" long-term " adaptation. Urgent adaptation occurs immediately after the start of the reaction stimulus and is carried out only preconfigured ready-made mechanisms on a physiological basis. At this stage of adaptation, the body's activity continues to mobilize an almost complete functional reserve at the limit of its physiological capabilities, so the adaptive effect is not fully realized and may not be permanent. Long-term adaptation occurs gradually as a result of long-term adaptation, or as a result of environmental influence: – urgent – based on repeated repetition of adaptation-the gradual quantitative accumulation of some changes, which in the body becomes an unadjusted adaptor. Thus, the process of adaptations, that is, the transition from the "urgent" stage to the "long-term" stage, expands the body's (individual's) constant life situations in New conditions, its range of residence in changing conditions and freedom of behavior.

Despite the fact that all people have mechanisms to regulate adaptation reactions are the same, the result of adaptation may differ even in the following cases the effect of the same stressor. Each individual person associated with this personality, its normal limits are functions that reflect the presence of functional reserves and its individual psychological characteristics. The problem of overcoming difficult life situations by an individual, and also

the study of personal resources as a means of overcoming such situations, is also reflected in many studies, and foreign authors (a.Ya. Ansupov, L.I.Ansiferova, R.M.Granovosky, F.B.Berezin, E.L.Dosenko, T.L.Kryukova, I.M.Nikolskaya, L.YU.Subbotina, R.Lazarus, R.Plutchik, N.Mcelliams, A.A.G.Maclakov, A.I.Shipilovs). Temperament, which is the basis of the structure of personality, acts as a regulator of behavior and related internal processes.

Temperament is derived from the Latin word-*temperamentum*||, which means||mix||. Scientific reasons for Temperament characteristics academic I.P.Pavlov's teaching on the types of elevated nerve activity revealed. I.P.Pavlov separates the four main types of nerve downstream, which correspond to the four temperament types of Hippocrates.

1- intense balanced and agile type. Typical type. This type forms the basis of temperament:

2- intense, balanced inert (sluggish) type heavy weight type. Forms the basis of phlegmatic temperament:

3-intense, but unbalanced, that is, intense, vibrant, type, in which The Nutcracker outperforms the braking. It forms the basis of the-choleric temperament:

4-weak type. Forms the basis of melancholic temperament.

Temperament is defined as the set of characteristics dynamic characteristics of its psyche by which the individual experiences activity (speed, rhythm, activity, intensity, emotionality, etc.), is hereditary and manifests itself in early life. The ratio of the following characteristics of the nervous system strength, mobility and balance forms the type of nervous system, which is the basis of physiological behavior: the strength of the nervous system speaks of a person's performance, his reaction characteristics stimuli and the ability to cope with stressful situations and mobility-about the speed of adaptation to environmental requirements. That is, temperament largely determines the typical way in which a person responds under the influence of the environment, thus an adaptive function. Among such reactions on the basis of individual reactions are considered natural features, psychological protective mechanisms (Nikolskaya, Granovskaya, Gladyshevs).). The doctrine of psychological protection of the individual was formed in the following framework of classical psychoanalysis theories.

The purpose of psychological protection is to reduce emotional stress and ensure the regulation of behavioral orientation. According to psychologists, psychological protection is a natural adaptation reaction of a person to life difficulties and refers to the initial stage of "urgent" adaptation. Psychological defense mechanisms can be used together with constructive methods of overcoming difficulties, and only the degree of extreme seriousness and intensity of protection is the dominant adaptation tool. Currently, the literature describes the experience of a number of studies on the relationship of temperament and psychological protective properties.

A. G. Samokhvalova, studying the problem of the best behavior of an individual, found that the psychological protection of an individual is associated with the type of temperament. The most common psychological protection for individuals of the sanguine type is intellectualization, substitution and suppression in them, and the least common is that regression is the preferred mechanism. Individuals of the choleric type often use protective mechanisms such as regression, reactivity, projection, and the least common is intellectualization. In individuals of the melancholic type, it uses regression, projection and intellectualization and rejects the least preferred. Individuals belonging to the phlegmatiktip

use the most projection, rejection, and intellectualization, with the least acceptable substitution being the mechanism.

L. A. Alexandrova, V. P. Mihailova, N. I. Korytchenkova, T. I. Kuvsinova found a psychological protective profile of the individual in life situations, by describing the typology of human behavior in difficult times, and is very broad compared to other types of temperament, which includes downstream defense mechanisms such as negation, substitution and regression. Downstream personality types sanguine temperament representatives use the most of the protective mechanisms of regression mechanism, rejection and repression. According to the authors, the harmony of personality structures is determined by the ratio of many individual characteristics, including temperament and psychological protection.

Research has shown that the most common protective mechanisms for individuals of the sanguine type have been identified - including leading in replacement, compensation, and projection mechanisms, and the least preferred in rejection protection mechanics. In individuals of the choleric type, however, personality protection mechanisms such as regression are often used, rejection and intellectualization, less often – the mechanism of repression. In individuals of the melancholic type, however, the himo mechanisms are the most obvious substitution, intellectualization and regression, and the mechanisms are the lesser levels-reactive formation. In individuals of the phlegmatic type, the protective profile includes repression, rejection, intellectualization.

As you can see, the data obtained by the authors of the above work sometimes differ and contradict each other. Nevertheless, taking into account the small amount, researchers have identified studies on the subject of interdependence of individual typological personal characteristics and the protective mechanisms it uses. It is in favor of continuing to study different relationships and is the components of a person's system of adaptation to complex life situations.

As a conclusion, it should be said that psychological protection mechanisms can lead to constructive as well as destructive effects. Protective mechanisms of a constructive nature, on the other hand, help to adequately assess the situation, identify an alternative goal and choose the optimal means in achieving it, and satisfy requirements and needs. Protective mechanisms of a destructive nature consist in the denial and violation of realism, which in time leads to a pathological change of personality. Therefore, the mechanisms of psychological protection protect the body from psychotraumatic disorders, situations, negative information and increase its stability in various situations. It should also be noted that psychological defense mechanisms can sometimes lead to severe consequences, personality formation, as well as a violation of social adaptation.

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